

TECHNOLOGIES FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF INFORMATION TECHNOLOGICAL COMPETENCE IN THE TRAINING OF FUTURE PRIMARY CLASS TEACHERS

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Abstract: in this thesis, opinions are given about the importance of using information technologies in the effective organization of primary education classes and their role in the development of students' oral and written speech.

Key words: multimedia tools, primary education, animation, information tools, technology, methodology.

Introduction:

Currently, educating young students, that is, training them at the level of a fully qualified specialist who can meet the requirements of state educational standards in all aspects, is one of the urgent tasks of our country.

There are specific aspects of the use of modern methods of education, pedagogical and information and communication technologies in the process of teaching subjects in the training of future primary school teachers. Use of textbooks, educational and methodical manuals, handouts, electronic materials, virtual stands and production samples and models of machines in working condition, watching television and radio broadcasts related to information technology, learned perform work methods, study information given in magazines and newspapers, use media tools to find terms related to information technology, perform didactic assignments, use information sources (television, radio, audio-video recording, telephone); it is important to follow media culture when opening files.

The socio-pedagogical necessity of an innovative approach to education in the current globalization processes is measured by:

1. Scientific-technical progress and socio-economic renewal of the continuous education system, in particular, improvement of the educational process in higher education institutions using the study of advanced foreign experiences, innovative approaches in education and information technologies;

2. Creation and implementation of effective organizational forms and technologies of person-oriented education that serve to develop the level of education, intellectual potential, social activity, and creativity skills of students and youth;

3. The need to develop the professional-innovative competence of the teacher in relation to mastering and implementing pedagogical innovations.

In the process of online teaching of subjects, when we use modern information and communication technologies of education, when we show presentations with the help of modern computer technologies in the practical classes held on science, students will gain deeper imagination and knowledge by seeing. In our opinion, the use of information and communication technologies in primary school classes gives a great positive result.

Another important aspect of the use of information and communication technologies is the formation of various labor skills by showing the training sessions "Master Classes" performed by our skilled carpenters, plumbers, cooks, tailors and craftsmen in various fields. It also provides an opportunity to start career guidance. For this, our technology teachers must have knowledge, skills, and qualifications in the field of information technologies. This information and communication competence (information and communication technology competence) is an important component of the professional competence of a teacher of technology education. We consider the professional competence of future teachers in the field of information and communication technologies as a necessary condition for ensuring the quality of educational results in the conditions of information.

"The information and communication technology skills of the future elementary school teacher are aimed at the practical use of information and communication technologies in their professional activities and are not limited to mastering the components of computer literacy. The competence of information and communication technologies is to a large extent not only knowledge, but also characteristic of the personal and professional activity of a specialist in the field of education, who is highly prepared for the purposeful and habitual use of all sets and various computer tools and technologies in his professional activity: a teacher, a college psychologist, a production foreman, a manager or head of an educational institution.

Formation and development of information and communication technology competence of future primary school teachers is carried out through theoretical and practical study of computer technologies for information processing:

- study software for different purposes (general, special, educational) and analyze the possibilities of using it in professional activities;

- changing the methodical system of science teaching, taking into account the possibility of using information and communication technologies, and

inculcating the culture of sharing pedagogical experience through telecommunication technologies, etc.

The professional activities of the future elementary school teacher in e-learning include:

- the ability to develop an electronic educational-methodological complex of the taught subject;
- the ability to use software tools to create interactive, multimedia electronic educational resources and use them;
- the ability to develop and conduct forms of network education (telecommunication projects, quizzes, teleconferences, Olympiads, etc.) for students;
- ability to use computer communication tools.

Modern trends in the development of electronic education are related to the use of the Hemis distance education site, which is based on the organization of joint activities of network users. Information communication technology and technological solutions for e-learning are focused on the use of distance learning systems (Hemis), which provide: automated management of the educational process, for the placement of educational content a single technological platform, planning the educational process and organizing remote communication between all participants of the educational process.

Thus, a mandatory component of the professional competence of a teacher in the field of e-learning is to know how to use the Hemis distance learning site to organize effective interaction of students. An important condition for the professional development of a future primary school teacher is his motivation for professional self-education. The motivational sphere of the student's self-education includes the following components.

- the motive of independence in the implementation of creative activity implies the possibility of the student to work autonomously on the preparation of author's programs;
- the motive of personal development is characterized by the desire for professional and career advancement;
- the motive of self-affirmation helps to generalize experience, prepare scientific and practical publications, open master classes;
- the competitive motive contributes to candidacy for prestigious professional competitions, awarding of titles, awards, recognition of colleagues.

Self-education means the activity of opening and enriching a person's spiritual needs, creativity, all personal possibilities. In the conditions of informatization of education, the self-educational activity of the teacher of vocational education is manifested in the research works conducted on a certain psychological, pedagogical, methodical topic in the context of virtual methodological associations. Today, independent study of the achievements of pedagogical science and advanced pedagogical practices is carried out with the help of electronic library materials, educational and innovative research online activities conducted by experienced teachers. The participation of a teacher of vocational education in lectures and speeches at distance seminars, conferences, pedagogical studies is an indicator of his desire to study.

In conclusion, we can emphasize that the use of modern information and communication technologies increases the motivation of the future elementary school teacher's self-education, because it helps to form and develop an individual style of creative and effective professional activity, helps to develop professional skills, qualities of professional activity and competence, and professional introspection skills.

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